

References

1. S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and G. PATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 947.
2. S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and G. PATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 1241.
3. S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and G. PATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.

Methanolysis of the Anhydride of 1-Carboxycyclohexane-1-Acetic Acid : A Comment.

JAYANTA K. RAY*

Department of Organic Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032.

Manuscript received 11 October 1977, accepted 25 January 1978

IN contradiction to the earlier reports by Khuda and Bhattacharya¹, who depicted the formation of the half-ester-acid (III) by methanolysis of the anhydride (I), Saharia and his co-workers² have recently reported that methanolysis of the anhydride (I) produces the isomeric half-ester-acid (II) as the only product.

- (II) R=CH₃; R'=H
 (III) R=H; R'=CH₃
 (IV) R=R'=C₂H₅
 (V) R=C₂H₅; R'=H
 (VI) R=R'=CH₃

In connection with synthetic studies in resin acids it was reported from this laboratory³ that partial hydrolysis of the diethyl ester (IV) gives the mono acid ester (V). Accordingly, partial hydrolysis (5% methanolic potassium hydroxide—1 hr) of the dimethyl ester (VI), [n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.51 (br s, 10H, methylene), 2.50 (br s, 2H methylene), 3.60 (s, 3H, -CH₂-COOCH₃) and 3.65 (s, 3H, -COOCH₃)] prepared from the corresponding diacid^{4,5} by esterification with an excess of ethereal diazomethane, produces the half-acid ester (II) as the major acidic product, m.p. 56° [¹H n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.50 (br s, 10H, methylene), 2.55 (br s, 2H, -CH₂-COOH), 3.65 (s, 3H, t-COOCH₃) and 10.00 (br s, 1H, COOH, exchangeable with D₂O)]. In the present study the methanolysis of anhydride (I) according to Saharia and his co-workers² afforded a mixture of two half-acid esters (II) and (III) containing Ca 10-15% of (II) as estimated from the integration ratio of the respective methyl ester singlets in the ¹H n.m.r. spectrum. After repeated column chromatography on silica gel using petroleum ether—ether (9:1), eluents furnished the pure half acid ester (III) [¹H n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.50 (br s, 10H methylene), 2.53 (br s, 2H, -CH₂-COOCH₃), 3.60 (s, 3H, -COOCH₃)

and 10.80 (s, 1H, —C—COOH, exchangeable with D₂O)] as a thick liquid. The present reinvestigation

thus confirms again the general observations⁶ recorded for the opening of substituted succinic anhydrides by treatment with alcohols.

The author thanks Prof. U. R. Ghatak for his suggestion to undertake this problem, which was brought to his notice by Dr. P. C. Bhattacharya, Department of Chemistry, Vidyasagar College, Calcutta.

References

1. M. QUDRAT-I-KHUDA and K. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 15.
2. H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI, R. K. GAUTAM and G. S. SAHARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1076.
3. U. R. GHATAK, N. N. SAHA and P. C. DUTTA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 79, 4487.
4. E. RO'YTHSTEIN and J. F. THORPE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2011.
5. A. LAPWORTH and J. A. M. RAE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2741.
6. M. S. NEWMAN, "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1956, p. 228; N. N. SAHA, B. K. GANGULY and P. C. DUTTA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 3670.

Chemical Investigation on *Polypodium juglandifolium* Don.

T. K. RAY, ASOK DASGUPTA, A. GOSWAMI,
D. R. MISRA and H. N. KHASTGIR*

Chemistry Department, North Bengal University,
Darjeeling, India.

and

JAMES N. SHOOLERY

Varian Associates, NMR Application Laboratory,
California 94303, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 20 January 1977, revised 18 October 1977,
accepted 6 December 1977

THE neutral fraction of the benzene extract of the fern *Polypodium juglandifolium* Don on careful chromatography afforded two hydrocarbons together with six alcohols shown in Table 1.

Fernene, flicene, cyclolaudenol and dryocrassol were identified by direct comparison with authentic specimens (m.m.p and Co-IR). The mother liquor from the crystallisation of cyclolaudenol was seen to be a mixture of two compounds one of which was cyclolaudenol (TLC). The mixture of alcohols (A), m.p. 121-22°, on acetylation gave an acetate (B), m.p. 107-108°, (α)_D + 55.17° and on catalytic hydrogenation in presence of Pd-C gave a compound (C), m.p. 132-34°, which on acetylation gave an acetate (D), m.p. 127-28°. NMR spectra of the original mixture (A) and its acetate (B)

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302.